

principal stresses, f_L, f_T, f_{LT} are the three independent material-fringe values, and α is the angle between σ_1 and the major-reinforcement direction, L-axis. By introducing the stress-strain relationship for anisotropic materials and employing the three independent strain-fringe values, Eq.(1) can also be written as

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1}{f_L^0} \left\{ \left[(\cos^2 \beta + \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} \sin^2 \beta) - (\sin^2 \beta + \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} \cos^2 \beta) \frac{f_L^0}{f_T^0} \right]^2 + \left[\left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1}\right) \frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0} \sin 2\beta \right]^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Fig.1 The coordinate

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the principal strains, β is the angle between ϵ_1 and the major-reinforcement direction, L-axis, and f_L^0, f_T^0, f_{LT}^0 are the strain-fringe values. It is obvious that the relationship between the material-fringe values and the strain-fringe values is given by

$$f_L^0 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_1 - E_2\nu_{12}} \quad f_T^0 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_2 - E_1\nu_{21}} \quad f_{LT}^0 = \frac{f_{LT}}{2G_{12}} \quad (3)$$

It may be noted that the degree of orthotropy exhibited by photoelastic composite materials is quite small and so there is no harm in assuming $f_L^0 \approx f_T^0$. Substituting Eq.(3) into Eq.(2), the linear relation between the principal-strain difference and the isochromatic-fringe order of orthotropic model is may be obtained

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2}{f_L^0} \left[\cos^2 2\beta + \left(\frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0}\right)^2 \sin^2 2\beta \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

Eq.(4) is a simplified formula. However, Eq.(4) is satisfied only when both principal strain-fringe values are equal each other. Agarwal considered the ratio f_L^0/f_T^0 to be close to 1 (between 1.056 and 0.9664)⁵. The strain-fringe values have been measured by the author through the test of tensile calibration specimens. Optical-characterization results for the test were found to be $f_L^0 = 3.1 \times 10^6$ m/fringe and $f_T^0 = 3.24 \times 10^6$ m/fringe. In view of the fact that the observed value $f_L^0/f_T^0 = 0.957$ is close to the results given by Agarwal. Hence Eq.(4) can be set down as an approximate solution. But in general the angle β in Eq.(4) cannot be directly measured through photoelastic experiments. However, it is of interest to note that the isoclinic parameters are observed to be close approach to the principal-strain directions of the orthotropic model.⁶ Therefore, as an approximation, employing directly the isoclinic parameter ϕ instead of the angle β in Eq.(4), a simplified strain-optic law can be obtained as

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2}{f_L^0} \left[\cos^2 2\phi + \left(\frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0}\right)^2 \sin^2 2\phi \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The error introduced by Eq.(5) is somewhat equivalent to the assuming $f_L^0 \approx f_T^0$ and $\beta \approx \phi$. The terms above are necessary to be verified through test. Based on the result provided by Agarwal⁵ the principal strains for models of orthotropic materials are calculated through Eq.(4) and Eq.(5) respectively and the errors are compared with each and all. The results of calculation are given in Table 1. In view of the fact that the computed results by employing Eq.(4) or Eq.(5) comparing with the experiments are still considered in good agreement, although the relative errors by employing Eq.(5) are big

slightly in some cases.

To verify the simplified strain-optic law, three unidirectionally reinforced tensile specimens oriented at 0 deg, 45 deg and 90 deg were fabricated⁷. For each of the three specimens the strain-fringe values of material and the isoclinical parameters were measured. The principal-strain difference and directions of principal strains were obtained through strain-gage measurements. The experimental results and comparison between measured values and computed values by employing Eq.(4) or Eq.(5) are given in Table 2, where the isoclinical parameter ϕ and angle β are initiated from the reinforced direction of material (L-axis) as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 Relationship between L-axis and angle

Table 1. Compute Results Based on Agarwal's Datum

Fiber Orientation (deg)	Fringe Order N	Isoclinic Angle ϕ' (deg)	Principal-Strain Angle β' (deg)	Principal-Strain Difference ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)			Error in Principal-strain Difference (%)	
				Experimental	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)
0	0.19	0	0	1747	1774	1774	-1.5	1.5
15	0.33	30	32.8	3260	3249	3245	0.3	0.46
30	0.5	43	43.2	5144	5141	5140	0.1	0.1
45	0.53	53	50.4	6036	6400	6396	-6.0	5.9
60	0.54	62	58.2	5720	5704	5969	0.3	0.4
75	0.49	72	70.3	4660	4798	4790	-3.0	2.7
90	0.44	90	90	3980	4531	4531	-13.8	13.8

Note: Isoclinic angle ϕ' and principal-strain angle β' provided by agarwal are all initiated from the X-axis.

Table 2. Comparison Between Measure and Compute Results

Fiber Orientation (deg)	Fringe Order N	Isoclinic Angle ϕ (deg)	Principal-Strain Angle β (deg)	Principal-Strain Difference ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)			Error in Principal-strain Difference (%)	
				Experimental	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)
0	0.27	0	0	820	837	837	2	2
45	0.77	4	4.15	2505	2375	2398	5.2	4.6
90	0.65	0	0	2236	2015	2015	9.8	9.8

CONCLUSIONS

For the convenience of engineering application, the method of orthotropic photo-elasticity must be simplified. An approximate analysis of orthotropic photoelasticity employing strain-optic law is provided due to the degree of orthotropic exhibited by photoelastic composite materials with respect to strain-optic properties is considerably small. The principal-strain difference and direction can be obtained from only two photoelastic measurements, the isochromatic-fringe order and isoclinic parameter, by means of the simplified strain-optic law proposed in this paper. This is an approximate method, but with the limited experiments showing a good agreement between the experimental results and predictions of the strain-optic law. Therefore, it is a practical orthotropic photoelastic analysis due to the error levels are within permissible range.

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